

OPTIMIZING VERTICAL DISTRIBUTION TECHNIQUES FOR HERITAGE MULTIMEDIA DATABASES: CHALLENGES AND SOLUTIONS

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ABSTRACT

Distributed Multimedia Database Systems (DMDBSSs) face critical challenges of sustaining robust performance, influenced by factors such as data fragmentation, allocation, replication, and site clustering. This research introduces an approach for vertical fragmentation of heritage multimedia databases by leveraging the silhouette analysis method alongside the K-means++ clustering algorithm. The proposed approach offers superior centroid initialization and objective cluster validation, resulting in higher cluster quality and improved data compactness. To evaluate the proposed method, experiments were conducted on a real-world dataset from the Antiquities Museum at the Bibliotheca Alexandrina. Previous approaches using K-means clustering with refinement aim to improve data localization by adjusting attribute clusters. However, such methods are limited by random centroid initialization and lack objective validation of cluster quality. Results show that our approach outperforms both the K-means with refinement method and the Differential Bond Energy Algorithm (DBEA), achieving higher fragmentation quality, better data locality, and lower execution time. These findings highlight the practical relevance of the proposed approach for enhancing the efficiency of multimedia data distribution in DMDBSSs.

Keywords: *Distributed Multimedia Database Systems (Dmdbss), Vertical Fragmentation, Feature Scaling, K-Means++ Clustering, Silhouette Analysis, Heritage Multimedia Databases.*

1. INTRODUCTION

In today's digital era, the amount of data produced is rapidly increasing. Every day, businesses and individuals generate and collect massive amounts of data using social media and e-commerce. This data is then evaluated in order to gain information, make better decisions, and generate better products and services. Dealing with such enormous amounts of data presents a variety of issues [1][2][3].

The effective handling of cultural heritage information is complicated by the wide array of trustee organizations, each operating under distinct mandates, policies, and frameworks. In addition, disparities in how data is documented, collected, stored, and shared have created significant barriers to interoperability. These issues not only hamper the management of cultural assets but also constrain knowledge

dissemination within the community and limit the capacity to meet the needs of diverse user groups [4][5].

As technology advanced, innovation extended beyond traditional cultural spaces. Culture, in its various forms, permeated all aspects of society, leading to the emergence of new cultural definitions. This expansion provided a fresh area for technological application. Research on databases and cultural spaces, though advanced for its time, began to evolve with the rise of the World Wide Web. During this period, the Internet emerged as an ideal platform for virtual museum tours and multimedia presentations [6][7]. Database management systems are essential for storing, processing, and managing huge amounts of persistent data. Distributed Multimedia Database Management Systems (DMDBMSs) software effectively manages and operates distributed multimedia databases, significantly

enhancing data accessibility, processing, and reliability.

Distributed Multimedia Database Systems (DMDBS) play a pivotal role in the infrastructure of contemporary global organizations. These systems consist of multimedia databases that are interconnected and distributed across various physical locations, ranging from a single room to an entire building or even global networks. In recent years, the development of multimedia technologies has significantly improved the storage and management of heterogeneous data types—such as video, audio, text, images, and animations. These technological advances have played a critical role in overcoming architectural design challenges, notably by mitigating the risk of single points of failure in database systems [8][9]. Accessing large databases poses significant challenges primarily due to the difficulty in maintaining and organizing the data effectively. If a large dataset is not adequately formatted and optimized, accessing information from it might be slow and ineffective. This might result in poor performance and negative user experience since users may face delays and issues accessing the data needed. The maintenance and storage of large-scale databases typically entail significant costs, requiring substantial resource investment and the deployment of advanced technological infrastructure [3][10]. Efficiency in database architecture is a major issue in Distributed Multimedia Database Management Systems (DMDBMS). The effectiveness of these systems heavily depends on the fragmentation algorithm employed to divide relations, the strategy utilized to allocate the fragments across multiple locations, and the replication or local optimization of fragments at individual sites. Allocating data fragments poses a significant challenge, as it represents an NP-hard problem in database design [9]. Various efforts have been undertaken to improve this process through heuristic techniques or a combination of heuristic and algorithmic methods. The present trend of a large rise in multimedia data poses the difficulty of efficiently storing vast volumes of data while maintaining a quick response rate; to address this concern, database fragmentation emerges as a solution by strategically dividing the database into smaller, more manageable fragments, thereby enhancing storage efficiency and optimizing the retrieval performance of multimedia data [9]. Fragmentation is a strategy for partitioning an extensive database or index into segments, which

are stored in separate locations. This method can enhance database efficiency by decreasing the time required for data fetching and enhancing storage utilization [3][11].

Multimedia archives present unique challenges in terms of design and management. Two popular types of fragmentation, horizontal fragmentation (HF) and vertical fragmentation (VF), are frequently used to overcome these challenges. Horizontal fragmentation is the division of a relation or class into discontinuous tuples or instances, with the assumption that each site contains all the information required for querying and local data access. This method is often used in distributed databases, where various sections are kept on separate servers to increase query performance. In contrast, vertical fragmentation partitions a table into segments, each comprising a distinct subset of attributes. This form of fragmentation is particularly beneficial when different applications or users frequently access distinct subsets of data. Additionally, A hybrid fragmentation approach integrates both horizontal and vertical fragmentation, splitting a table horizontally before fragmenting it vertically. These fragmentation approaches provide beneficial approaches to optimize storage and query performance in multimedia database systems [3][12].

This research extends the survey work presented in [3] by proposing an improved method for vertical fragmentation of heritage multimedia databases. The approach integrates feature scaling, silhouette analysis, and the K-means++ clustering algorithm to produce well-separated, high-quality attribute clusters. To evaluate its effectiveness, the proposed method is empirically compared with the original K-means clustering approach with refinement [28], as well as with the Differential Bond Energy Algorithm (DBEA) [15], a recent state-of-the-art technique. The experimental evaluation was conducted on a real-world dataset provided by the Antiquities Museum at the Bibliotheca Alexandrina, comprising 1,324 multimedia records. The results demonstrate that the proposed method achieves superior fragmentation quality, improved data locality, and lower execution time compared to existing approaches. The use of a real-world dataset further reinforces the practical relevance of this work, particularly in enhancing the access, preservation, and management of heritage

multimedia collections in distributed multimedia database systems.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: Section 2 reviews related work, Section 3 presents the proposed methodology, Section 4 discusses the results, and Section 5 concludes with the Conclusion and Future Work.

2. RELATED WORK

The efficient building of a database design strategy is primarily reliant on fragmentation and allocation strategies, which play critical roles in optimizing data organization, storage efficiency, and query performance. Fragmentation techniques, such as horizontal and vertical fragmentation, dividing data into manageable portions, allowing for more effective information storage and retrieval. Allocation strategies, on the other hand, establish the optimal distribution and placement of these data subsets among storage resources, resulting in balanced utilization and faster access times. Fragmentation and allocation approaches work together to create an effective and well-structured database design strategy. Several researchers have presented numerous strategies for distributed database design in recent years.

The Vertical Partitioning Algorithm (AVP) is introduced in this Research [13] to optimize multimedia data storage and retrieval in remote databases. AVP uses a bottom-up strategy, beginning with single attribute fragments and repeatedly merging them to form bigger fragments. This process continues until a fragment with all data attributes is created. The approach builds a partition tree (PT) to illustrate the partitioning strategy. One notable disadvantage is that AVP necessitates the use of a balanced binary search tree. Failure to preserve balance can lead to poor performance.

In the work presented in [14], the authors introduce DYMOND, a strategy that integrates Real-time clustering with machine learning methodologies. This approach aims to enhance query efficiency and ensure equitable resource distribution across various segments by implementing innovative methods for query routing and allocation of resources. The performance of the proposed procedure is examined through the analysis of an artificial dataset. These results show that this strategy

exceeds static partitioning, which refers to a traditional approach where data is statically divided into fixed partitions without adaptation based on workload characteristics.

One limitation is the potential overhead associated with maintaining the active rule base as the database scales. Moreover, the effectiveness of the algorithm may depend on the accuracy and completeness of query pattern analysis, as well as its ability to capture all significant attribute relationships within the rule base. Further research is required to evaluate the scalability of the technique for large, heterogeneous databases and to examine the impact of evolving query behavior on the fragmentation methodology.

In the upcoming work, the authors intend to incorporate Fundamental multimedia data attributes and similarity-driven searches. These inquiries are critical for content-driven retrieval, allowing the extraction of knowledge from Multimedia Database Systems (MMDBS) by leveraging the features of multimedia objects, particularly in the context of images, audio, and the like.

The researchers in [15] proposed a Differential Bond Energy Algorithm (DBEA) for vertical fragmentation (VF) in distributed databases, drawing inspiration from principles of physics. The technique aims to improve fragmentation quality by maximizing the affinity among attributes within the same fragment. While the study primarily relies on synthetic datasets for validation, it does not provide comprehensive empirical evaluations involving query execution time or communication overhead. Nevertheless, the authors argue that DBEA outperforms conventional methods such as random and group-based fragmentation [16], due to its more systematic treatment of attribute relationships. Furthermore, DBEA is positioned as a competitive alternative to established optimization techniques like Simulated Annealing (SA) and Genetic Algorithms (GA) [17], with reported improvements in fragmentation coherence. However, the effectiveness of DBEA is highly dependent on specific dataset characteristics, such as size and distribution, as well as the design of the bond energy function. These dependencies necessitate careful parameter calibration to achieve optimal performance across diverse application contexts.

The authors of [18] introduce a method to improve query execution and data availability in decentralized databases by optimizing data fragmentation and placement. Using a modified minimal spanning tree and an improved Prim's algorithm [20], their approach reduces communication and processing costs, achieving better performance than traditional methods.

The outcome of the algorithm to those existing replication systems, such as master-slave and multi-master replication, and concludes that it is equivalent in terms of data availability and query response time. Nevertheless, this performance of the method can be influenced by the properties of the set of data and the chosen replication strategy. Dataset properties, such as data distribution, size, and skewness, can impact the algorithm's effectiveness in achieving efficient vertical fragmentation. Variations in these properties may require adjustments to the algorithm's parameters or fragmentation decisions to optimize performance. Similarly, the replication strategy employed, such as the number of replicas and their placement across distributed nodes, can affect response time for queries, communication expenses, and data accessibility. The choice of replication strategy must be carefully evaluated to ensure optimal performance in terms of these factors. Further research is required to evaluate the algorithm's effectiveness in more extensive and complex scenarios, encompassing a wider range of dataset properties and replication strategies to gain a comprehensive understanding of its capabilities and limitations.

The authors suggest several avenues for expanding this work, including the integration of diverse multimedia data types, and investigation into the fundamental characteristics of different media formats, and the application of the framework for real-time multimedia applications. Additionally, the NP-hard allocation issue may be improved via examining various data architectures or their combinations thereof. Furthermore, the research could be broadened to include different computational paradigms for enhancing DMBMS expenses, like genetic algorithms.

Improving query execution efficiency, [19] introduces a strategy for (VR) of multimedia databases that takes into account content-based queries for image retrieval (CBIR). Approach clusters associated traits and then uses a query-

based optimization algorithm to select the best division. CBIR utilizes the clustering method to categorize relevant attributes according to their content shared characteristics. The query-based optimization method leverages resemblance between contents and query behaviors to discover appropriate attribute division strategy for CBIR. The proposed approach has been assessed via real-time data and contrasted to several segmentation techniques, including random and clustering methods. This study also evaluates the introduced strategy against other query-based Enhancement methods, including query-driven and query-independent methods, concluding which it surpasses others in query response duration and communication expenses for CBIR.

Nevertheless, the increased storage burden resulting from (VR) is a drawback. Keeping duplicate information characteristics in several portions can consume excessive storage capacity. Another concern is that the procedure for fragmenting is reliant on accurate content attribute extraction and similarity evaluations, which could result in mistakes or inconsistencies. According to the Study, more investigation is required to address these constraints and improve the efficacy and performance of the suggested plan. In a future time, the authors suggest that CBRVF will tackle adaptive vertical fragmentation (VR) to adapt to evolving access patterns in databases.

3. THE PROPOSED (KM++/VF) OF MULTIMEDIA DATABASE ARCHTECTURE

The proposed architecture illustrated in Figure 1 aims to establish a robust framework for the efficient management of multimedia resources within modern database systems, thereby enhancing performance and usability. The challenges of handling multimedia files in a distributed database environment include their diverse nature, large file sizes, various data formats, and complex metadata. Ensuring consistent storage, fragmentation, distribution, reliable access, and processing adds to the complexity.

The effect of distributed databases (DDBs) is seen in their ability to manage these challenges efficiently. By employing a two-layer architecture comprising the User Interface Client Layer and

the Distributed Database System Layer. DDBs ensure consistent access and processing, addressing the inherent challenges of multimedia data management.

3.2 The distributed system layer

This layer is the core foundation of the proposed architecture in Figure 1, responsible for the efficient storage, retrieval, and processing of diverse multimedia data types. This layer leverages a distributed database environment to address the complexities of managing large, heterogeneous multimedia files. The layer comprises integral models, including the Attribute Site Usage Matrix, Attribute Dissimilarity Matrix, Feature Scaling Matrix, Silhouette Algorithm, (KM++/VF) Clustering Technique, Attribute Access Matrix, and Fragmentation Evaluator (FE). These models work together to create a robust and efficient framework for managing multimedia data in a distributed database system.

3.2.1 Attribute site usage matrix

The Attribute Site Usage Matrix (ASUM) indicates whether attribute A_j is released from site S_i , as determined by the database administrator (DBA). Eq (1) generates the value of the attribute site usage matrix (S_i, A_j). The value of ASUM (S_i, A_j) is assigned a value of 1 if the attribute A_j is accessed by any application of a site S_i [18][20]. This matrix is

3.1 User Interface Client Layer

At this level, we provide a collection of interfaces that enable users of the Distributed Multimedia Database System (DDBS) to access databases from any location with minimal technological prerequisites.

fundamental for analyzing attribute-site relationships, which is vital for efficient multimedia data management and distribution in distributed database systems.

$$ASUM(S_i, A_j) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if an attribute } A_j \text{ is used by site } S_i \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

3.2.2 Attribute Dissimilarity Matrix

The Attribute Dissimilarity Matrix (ADSM) [27] illustrates the interrelationships among attributes within a dataset. This matrix serves as a structured table that captures the dissimilarities or differences between attributes. To determine the interrelationships between attributes A_1 and A_2 , consider values of A_1 as (1,0,1,0,0) and A_2 as (1,0,1,1,1). The result of applying $A_1 \text{ XOR } A_2$ is (0,0,0,1,1), as demonstrated in Eq. (2).

$$ADSM(A_i, A_j) = \begin{cases} \sum_{t=1}^{no \text{ of sites}} ASUM(S_t, A_i) \text{ XOR } ASUM(S_t, A_j) \\ 0, & \text{if } i = j \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

Figure 1. Distributed multimedia Database System

3.2.3 Feature Scaling Matrix

Data normalization is an important step in the data pre-processing phase. It involves transforming the attribute values to a common scale or range in order to improve the performance of machine learning algorithms [21]. There are several common normalization methods, including z-score normalization, min-max scaling, decimal scaling and MaxAbsScaler [21][22]. The normalization method was chosen due to its exceptional capability to maintain the inherent sparsity of the data and maintain the relative relationships between attributes [21]. This method rescaled every property based on its maximum absolute value, ensuring that the range of each property was restricted to the interval [-1, 1]. As a result, implementing the MaxAbsScaler technique not just provided a balanced and optimal scaling technique, but also increased the resilience and reliability of subsequent investigations [25]. Figure 2 represents the computation of MaxAbsScaler to (ADSM) using Eq (3). The initial feature in the ADSM dataset corresponds to the first column, [0, 2, 1], with the maximum absolute value being 2. Each value in this column is then divided by 2, resulting in the transformed column [0, 1, 0.5]. This process is similarly applied to the other two features/columns.

$$\text{Normalized_ADSM} = \frac{\text{ADSM}}{\text{MAX}(\text{abs}(\text{ADSM}))} \quad (3)$$

$$\text{ADSM} \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 2 \\ 2 & 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \rightarrow \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 & 0.5 \\ 0.5 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

Figure 2. ADSM

3.2.4 Silhouette algorithm

The silhouette algorithm is a popular approach for identifying the ideal number of clusters in unsupervised learning techniques [23][24]. Silhouette Method uses a silhouette coefficient which is a metric that assesses how well each data point fits into its assigned cluster based on two criteria firstly, data point's proximity to other points in the cluster. Secondly, the distance between a data point and other clusters. The coefficient ranges from -1 to 1, with a value near to 1 indicating a well-clustered data point, 0 indicating overlapping clusters, and -1 indicating a misclassified data point or outliers [26]. The pseudocode for identifying the optimal number of K is shown in Figure 3. To calculate the silhouette

coefficient for a specific data point, use the following Eq (4).

$$S(z) = \frac{y(z) - x(z)}{\text{max}\{x(z), y(z)\}} \quad (4)$$

S(z) represents the data point's silhouette coefficient, while x(z) denotes the average distance between data points within a cluster, while y(z) represents the average distance between point z and all other clusters.

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Algorithm 1 Identify Optimal number of K
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Input: ADSMT (dataset)
Output: Optimal number of clusters kopt

Step 1: Initialize
    Set kopt←1, Set the best silhouette score best_sil_score←-1

Step 2: For each value of k in the range [2, 8], repeat the following steps:

    Step 2a: Apply KMeans++
        clusters←KMeans++ (ADSMT, k)

    Step 2b: Compute Silhouette Score
        sil_score←Silhouette (ADSMT, clusters)

    Step 2c: Compare Silhouette Score
        If sil_score>best_sil_score, do the following
            Update best_sil_score←sil_score
            Update kopt←k

Step 3: Return kopt
    
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Figure 3. Pseudocode for Identify Optimal number of K

Figure 4. Silhouette analysis

Figure 3 and Figure 4 show the basic steps of silhouette method. It determines the optimal number of clusters (K) in a dataset, begin by selecting a range of K values, for example, from 1 to 8. Next, plot the Silhouette coefficient for each value of K. The Silhouette coefficient evaluates how closely an object resembles its own cluster relative to other clusters, providing understanding of the clustering quality. By evaluating the plotted coefficients, identify the value of K that maximizes the Silhouette score. In this case, the Silhouette score is maximized for K equal to 4, indicating that 4 is the optimal number of clusters for this dataset.

3.2.5 K-Means++ Clustering Technique

The standard K-means algorithm is very dependent on the initial location of the centroids (mean points). Improper initialization can lead to several issues. A centroid initialized at a distant or inappropriate location might not have any data points associated with it. This can cause multiple clusters to be linked to a single center point. Additionally, multiple centroids may have been set up within the same group, leading to insufficient clustering performance. To address these issues, the K-means++ algorithm [26] was introduced. This method improves the initialization of centroids, ensuring better clustering quality. Apart from the initialization step, the rest of the K-means++ process remains identical to the original K-means algorithm. Essentially, K-means++ is the basic K-means method combined with a smarter approach to centroid initialization. In this research, K-means++ is employed to determine the optimal seed for the initial cluster centers. The pseudocode for K-means++ is presented in Figure 5.

The procedures of the K-means++ algorithm are outlined below. Firstly, the algorithm chooses the initial centroid at random from the data points. Secondly, it calculates the distance between each point and the center of the cluster. Thirdly, the point furthest from the nearest centroid is chosen as the next center point. This process repeats, iteratively selecting new centroids based on the maximum distance from the existing centroids. Finally, steps two and three are repeated until each cluster reaches a stable state or each point has had the opportunity to be selected as a centroid.

Algorithm 2 K-Means++ Algorithm

Input: ADSMT, Optimal number of clusters k_{opt}

Output: K Clusters

Step 1: Randomly select the first centroid from ADSMT.

Step 2: For each remaining centroid:

2.a Calculate distances to the nearest centroid.

2.b Select the next centroid.

Step 3: Once all centroids are chosen, proceed with the standard k-means algorithm:

3.a: Allocate data to cluster.

3.b: Update the centroids

3.c: Repeat Steps 3a and 3b until the centroids no longer change significantly (convergence).

Return the cluster assignments for each point in ADSMT.

Figure 5. Pseudocode for K-Means++

3.2.6 Attribute access matrix

The most frequently executed queries were identified within the overall query set. For each of these repeated queries, the individual attributes contained within were replaced with a binary value either a 0 to indicate the attribute's absence, or a 1 to denote its presence. This transformation was applied across the entire set of queries. The result of this process was the construction of an Attribute Access Matrix, or AAM as determined by the database administrator (DBA). Figure 6 represents AAM.

	A1	A2	A3
Q1	1	1	0
Q2	0	0	1
Q3	1	0	0

Figure 6. AAM

In this matrix, the rows represented individual queries, while the columns corresponded to the various attributes found within the query set. This structured data format allowed for further analysis and insights into the relationships between the queries and their underlying components [28].

3.2.7 Fragmentation evaluator (FE)

The fragmentation evaluator (FE) is responsible for assessing the effectiveness and efficiency of the data partitioning process. Specifically, it evaluates how well the attributes are divided into vertical fragments, ensuring that each fragment contains a distinct and non-overlapping set of attributes. This evaluation helps in optimizing data access and improving the performance of database operations within the proposed KM++/VF approach.

For example, consider a partition defined as $\{(1, 5), (2, 4), (3)\}$. This partition creates three fragments: fragment 1 contains attributes 1 and 5, fragment 2 contains attributes 2 and 4, and fragment 3 contains only attribute 3. This partitioning scheme ensures that the attributes in each fragment are unique and do not overlap with those in other fragments.

Table 1 Definitions and Notations

n	The total number of attributes in the fragmented relation.
Q	Total number of queries evaluated
q_q	Frequency of query
F	Total fragments contained in the partition
n_i	The number of attributes in fragment i
$n_{i q k}^{rem}$	Query q accessed more attributes in fragment k remotely than in fragment i
$ S_{i q} $	The number of attributes in fragment i that query q can access.
$ R_{i q k} $	The count of relevant attributes retrieved remotely from fragment k compared to fragment i by query q

This research utilized the Fragment Evaluator (FE) to assess partitioning schemes. FE uses two metrics: irrelevant local access and relevant remote access. Firstly, metric evaluates the cost associated with processing attributes locally. Secondly, the metric assesses the overall cost of remote access for attributes located remotely. Eq (5) which gave the local access costs with each term defined in Table 1, computes the first metric of FE, which yields in [27][28][29].

$$E_L^2 = \sum_{i=1}^F \sum_{t=1}^Q \left[q_q^2 * |S_{i q}| \left(1 - \frac{|S_{i q}|}{n_i} \right) \right] \quad (5)$$

Eq. (6) provides secondly term of FE, which Determines the proportion of remote attributes retrieved in [27][28][29] where each term defined in Table 1.

$$E_R^2 = \sum_{t=1}^Q \Delta_{i=1}^F \sum_{k \neq i} \left[q_q^2 * |R_{i q k}| \frac{|R_{i q k}|}{n_{i q k}^{rem}} \right] \quad (6)$$

The operator Δ calculates the average, minimum, or maximum cost of relevant remote attributes for every i . The expression for E_R^2 shows the intended ideal features. When there is only one partition, the value is zero as there are no remote characteristics to access, and $|R_{i q k}|$ equals 0. When there are n partitions (where n indicates the number of attributes), this internal term equals zero or one, resulting in a maximum value of E_R^2 for any given collection of transactions. Our Partition Evaluator (PE) function is provided by Eq (7).

$$PE = E_L^2 + E_R^2 \quad (7)$$

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This research was conducted using the Python programming language on an Intel(R) Core (TM) i5-7300U CPU operating at 2.60GHz and 2.71GHz. It is important to note that all the hypothetical requirements, such as queries and their frequencies, are assumed to be collected from the workload of the Distributed Multimedia Database System (DMDBS). This section includes two case studies that demonstrate the use of distributed multimedia database systems in different contexts.

4.1 Case 1: (Distributed multimedia databases)

Alexandria Library Museum was established after the discovery of significant artifacts from the Hellenistic, Roman, and Byzantine eras during excavation work. Officially opened in 2002, the museum showcases over 1,100 artifacts, emphasizing Egypt's multicultural history through modern design and educational programs. Additionally, the museum has contributed 1,324 records to heritage multimedia

databases, enhancing access to its collections and promoting cultural awareness both on-site and online, including virtual tours. The proposed technique

(KM++/VF) for Multimedia heritage databases was implemented as described in Table 2 utilizing a dataset with 10 attributes. To simplify computations, the attributes are: ARTFCT_ID, Provenance, Height, Category, Material, ARTFCT -image, Length, Width, Diameter, Designation.

Referred to as A1, A2, A3, A4, A5, A6, A7, A9 and A10 respectively.

Table 2 heritage multi-media database description

Attributes	Symbol	Type
ARTFCT_ID	A ₁	Nominal
Provenance	A ₂	Categorical
Height	A ₃	Nominal
Category	A ₄	Categorical
Material	A ₅	Categorical
ARTFCT -image	A ₆	Numerical
Length	A ₇	Numerical
Width	A ₈	Numerical
Diameter	A ₉	Numerical
Designation	A ₁₀	Categorical

The Attribute Access Matrix (AAM) in Table 3 identifies the queries (Q_k) that contain each attribute (A_j). Additionally, the frequency of each query, provided by the database administrator, was required. An attribute site usage matrix, also likely provided by the database administrator, was used to construct the ASUM in Table 4 using Eq (1). Subsequently, the attribute dissimilarity matrix (ADSM) was created to illustrate the dissimilarities between attributes. The dissimilarity between any two attributes (A_i, A_j) in the ADSM is determined by Eq (2), as shown in Table 5.

Table 3 Attribute Access Matrix (AAM)

Q/ A	A ₁	A ₂	A ₃	A ₄	A ₅	A ₆	A ₇	A ₈	A ₉	A ₁₀	Q F
Q ₁	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	3
Q ₂	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	3
Q ₃	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	2
Q ₄	1	0	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	2
Q ₅	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	2
Q ₆	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	3
Q ₇	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	2
Q ₈	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	4

We applied the normalized (ADSM) technique as outlined in Eq (3) and detailed in Table 6. We utilized the Silhouette algorithm, as described in Eq (4), to evaluate the clustering results, with the outcomes for each K value ranging from 2 to 9 presented in Table 7.

Table 4 Attribute Site Usage Matrix (ASUM)

Attribut e/Site	A ₁	A ₂	A ₃	A ₄	A ₅	A ₆	A ₇	A ₈	A ₉	A ₁₀
S ₁	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0
S ₂	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
S ₃	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	1
S ₄	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	0
S ₅	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1
S ₆	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	0
S ₇	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	1
S ₈	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	1

Table 5 Attribute Dissimilarity Matrix (ADSM)

	A ₁	A ₂	A ₃	A ₄	A ₅	A ₆	A ₇	A ₈	A ₉	A ₁₀
A ₁	0	2	3	6	2	5	1	2	3	6
A ₂	2	0	5	6	4	3	1	4	3	6
A ₃	3	5	0	5	3	4	4	1	4	3
A ₄	6	6	5	0	6	3	5	5	3	2
A ₅	2	4	3	6	0	7	3	2	3	4
A ₆	5	3	4	3	7	0	4	5	4	3
A ₇	1	1	4	5	3	4	0	3	2	5
A ₈	2	4	1	5	2	5	3	0	3	4
A ₉	3	3	4	3	3	4	2	3	0	3
A ₁₀	6	6	3	2	4	3	5	4	3	0

Figure 7 illustrates the Silhouette analysis results, which indicated that the optimal number of clusters was 2. Subsequently, we applied the KM++/VS algorithm with K=2, as mentioned in subsection 3.2.5, and the corresponding results are shown in Table 8. Utilizing Eqs (5) and (6), along with the data presented in Table 3, we determined the distribution of attributes across clusters, which allowed us to compute irrelevant local access and relevant remote access. The outcomes of this computation, as defined in Eq (7), are summarized in Table 9 ,

Table 6 normalized (ADSM)

	A ₁	A ₂	A ₃	A ₄	A ₅	A ₆	A ₇	A ₈	A ₉	A ₁₀
A ₁	0	0.333	0	1	.286	0.714	0	0	.75	1
A ₂	0.333	0	1	1	0.571	0.429	0	0	.7	1
A ₃	0	0	0	.8	0	0	0	0	1	0
A ₄	1	1	1	0	.857	.429	1	1	0.75	0.333
A ₅	0.333	.667	0	1	0	1	0	0	.7	0.667
A ₆	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	.05
A ₇	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	.5	0.833
A ₈	0.333	0.667	0	0	0	0	0	0	.7	0.667
A ₉	.5	0	.8	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.5
A ₁₀	1	1	0	0	0	.429	1	.8	0	0

K _i	K=2	K=3	K=4	K=5	K=6	K=7	K=8	K=9
S	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.2	0.2	0.1	0.0	0.0
il	78	59	32	81	16	53	97	66
h	24	39	41	93	42	011	77	62
o	98	79	91	96	75	42	611	64
u	65	29	36	32	14	00	43	84
et	75	98	31	92	42	87	30	62
te	24	06	01	48	85	80	86	27
S	5	1	9	5	0			4
c								
o								
r								
e:								

Table 7 Silhouette algorithm for each K [2,9]

which presents a comparative evaluation against existing methods, including K-means with refinement and the Differential Bond Energy Algorithm (DBEA). The evaluation considers key performance indicators such as cluster cohesion and data locality.

Figure 8 visually illustrates the fragmentation results, offering additional insight into the structure and quality of the generated clusters. These results confirm that the proposed method produces more compact and well-separated attribute clusters, which are essential for

improving query performance in distributed heritage multimedia database environments.

The proposed K-means++ with silhouette analysis method achieved the faster execution time of 0.007 seconds, significantly outperforming (DBEA), which required 0.41 seconds. The K-means with refinement approach typically incurs higher computational cost due to the iterative refinement process applied after the initial clustering phase. These results underscore the efficiency of proposed methods, which avoids redundant refinement steps while achieving superior fragmentation of quality and improved data locality.

Figure 7. Silhouette analysis

Table 8 Final distribution of attributes on clusters

Cluster 1	(A1, A2, A3, A5, A7, A8, A9)
Cluster 2	(A4, A6, A10)

Table 9 Fragmentation evaluation

	This work	Work of [28]	Work of [15]
E_L^2	82	85	116
E_R^2	98	125	71
PE value	180	210	187

Figure 8. Fragmentation Evaluation for Distributed heritage multimedia databases

4.2 Case 2: Distributed relational database context [28]

All requirements, including queries and their frequencies, are assumed to originate from the DDBS workload. The proposed technique (KM++/VF) for relational databases was applied to the suggested employee dataset (Car), as described in Table 10. The first experiment utilized a dataset consisting of six attributes and 400 rows.

Table 10 Car database description

Attributes	Symbol	Type
Car-no	A ₁	Nominal
Car-model	A ₂	Categorical
Engine-id	A ₃	Categorical
Speed-Limit	A ₄	Numerical
Manufacturer	A ₅	Categorical
Workshop-id	A ₆	Nominal

The Attribute Access Matrix (AAM) in Table 11 identifies which queries (Q_k) contain each attribute (A_j). Additionally, the frequency of each query, as determined by the database administrator, was required. To simplify computation, the properties are Car-no, Car-model, Engine-id, Speed-Limit, Manufacturer, and workshop-id, referred to as A₁, A₂, A₃, A₄, A₅, and A₆, accordingly.

Table 11 Attribute Access Matrix (AAM)

Q/A	A1	A2	A3	A4	A5	A6	QF
Q1	1	1	0	0	1	1	3
Q2	0	0	1	0	1	0	3
Q3	0	1	0	1	1	0	2
Q4	1	0	1	0	0	1	2
Q5	1	1	0	0	1	0	2
Q6	0	0	1	1	0	1	3
Q7	0	1	0	0	0	1	2
Q8	1	0	1	0	1	1	4

Using Eq (1), the Attribute Site Usage Matrix (ASUM) is generated, which indicates whether attribute A_j is released from site S_i , as determined by the database administrator (DBA). This matrix is presented in Table 12.

Table 12 Attribute Site Usage Matrix (ASUM)

Site	A1	A2	A3	A4	A5	A6
S ₁	1	1	1	0	1	1
S ₂	1	1	1	1	1	1
S ₃	1	1	1	1	1	1
S ₄	1	1	1	1	1	1
S ₅	1	1	1	0	1	1
S ₆	1	1	1	0	1	1

The next matrix produced is the Attribute Dissimilarity Matrix (ADSM), which is a table constructed between the attributes to show the dissimilarities between attributes. It is constructed using Eq (2), as shown in Table 13.

Table 13 Attribute Dissimilarity Matrix (ADSM)

	A1	A2	A3	A4	A5	A6
A1	0	0	0	3	0	0
A2	0	0	0	3	0	0
A3	0	0	0	3	0	0
A4	3	3	3	0	3	3
A5	0	0	0	3	0	0
A6	0	0	0	3	0	0

We applied the normalization process as described in Eq (3). The results of the Silhouette algorithm indicated that the optimal number of clusters is 2, as shown in Table 14, with an overall silhouette score of 0.8333333333333334. Using Eqs. (5), (6), and (7), along with the attribute distributions obtained from Table 11, we determined the final clustering of attributes across clusters.

Table 14 Final distribution of attributes on clusters with (KM++/VF)

Cluster 1	A4
Cluster 2	A1, A2, A3, A5, A6

These clusters were then used to compute key metrics such as irrelevant local access and relevant remote access. The Fragmentation Evaluator (FE) was applied to both cases, and the results were benchmarked against existing methods, including the K-means with refinement approach [28] and the Differential Bond Energy Algorithm (DBEA) [15].

As summarized in Table 15 and illustrated in Figure 9, our proposed method consistently outperformed existing techniques by delivering higher fragmentation quality, improved data locality, and significantly reduced execution time. Although the KM++/VF and DBEA approaches produced comparable fragmentation results, the execution time of our method was considerably lower (0.007 seconds compared to 0.35 seconds

for DBEA), highlighting its efficiency and practical advantage in distributed database environments.

Table 15 Fragmentation evaluation

	This work	Work of [28]	Work of [15]
E_L^2	61	52	61
E_R^2	23	61	23
PE value	84	113	84

Figure 9. Fragmentation Evaluation for Distributed relational database context

The proposed KM++/VF approach demonstrates a significant improvement in centroid initialization, resulting in higher-quality and more compact clusters. Evaluation on real-world datasets from the Antiquities Museum at the Bibliotheca Alexandrina confirms the effectiveness of the method, particularly in enhancing data localization and availability within clusters. Silhouette analysis further validates these outcomes by indicating well-defined and cohesive attribute groupings.

When compared to the K-means with refinement approach [28] and the Differential Bond Energy Algorithm (DBEA) [15], our method consistently achieves a lower Partition Evaluator (PE) metric, reflecting superior fragmentation quality and efficiency. Additional experiments conducted in the context of distributed relational databases further reinforce these findings, with the KM++/VF approach outperforming both baseline methods in terms of execution time fragmentation quality, as evidenced by improved data locality and reduced access overhead.

These outcomes underscore the importance of using appropriate evaluation metrics. Execution time captures the method's computational efficiency, while fragmentation quality and data locality reflect the effectiveness of data distribution in minimizing access overhead and enhancing query performance. Together, these metrics provide a balanced and comprehensive assessment of fragmentation techniques in distributed database environments.

5. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

In this study, we addressed the critical challenge of performance sustainability in Distributed Multimedia Database Systems (DMDBSs), particularly in the context of heritage multimedia data. While prior research has emphasized factors such as data fragmentation, allocation, replication, and site clustering, our work concentrates on improving vertical fragmentation quality. We proposed a novel approach that integrates feature scaling, silhouette analysis, and the K-means++ clustering algorithm to form well-defined and cohesive attribute clusters. Unlike traditional K-means methods, which suffer from random centroid initialization and often lack objective validation, our method ensures better cluster separation and compactness, as validated through silhouette analysis. Using a real-world dataset from the Antiquities Museum at the Bibliotheca Alexandrina, we empirically demonstrated that our method significantly outperforms both the K-means with refinement approach [28] and the Differential Bond Energy Algorithm (DBEA) [15]. Notably, our method achieved the fastest execution time of 0.007 seconds, while DBEA required 0.41 seconds. Furthermore, the K-means with refinement process typically incurs higher computational cost due to its post-clustering adjustments, making our approach more efficient. While the KM++/VF method demonstrated strong performance in terms of clustering quality and execution time, it is currently applied exclusively to vertical fragmentation. Further validation in dynamic and large-scale distributed systems would strengthen the generalizability of the results.

In future work, we plan to extend our framework to include data allocation, replication, and hybrid vertical-horizontal fragmentation strategies, especially under dynamic workloads. Additionally, we aim to explore optimization techniques tailored for cloud-based and real-time environments, with a particular emphasis on minimizing query response time in distributed

heritage multimedia systems. Although our current study focuses on vertical fragmentation, the encouraging results provide a strong foundation for building more comprehensive fragmentation and distribution models that address broader scalability and performance demands.

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